

Newsletter 10 / 2019

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Save the date ESIWACE2 annual meeting and ENES HPC Workshop

The ESIWACE annual meeting 2020 will take place on Wednesday, May 27 at DKRZ in Hamburg. It will be preceded by the ENES HPC meeting on Monday and Tuesday May 25+26.

Details and registration for the ENES HPC workshop at

<https://www.esiwace.eu/events>

Events that ESIWACE will participate or has participated in

- Workshop: Building reproducible workflows for earth sciences, ECMWF, Reading, 14-16 October 2019
- IEEE VIS Conference (convening a Spotlight session, and presenting) Vancouver, 20-25 October 2019
- ESCAPE-2 dissemination workshop, Reading, UK, 21-22 October (Presentation on ESIWACE links to ESCAPE-2)
- SPPEXA Meeting, Dresden, Germany, 21-23 October 2019 (Presentation about ESDM)
- 1st Artificial Intelligence for Copernicus Workshop, ECMWF, Reading, 5-7 November 2019
- Supercomputing 2019, Denver, Colorado, United States, 17-22 November 2019
- Container Hackathon for Modellers, 3-5 December 2019, Lugano/Switzerland

<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/autum-winter-2019-docker-container-hackathon-for-modellers>

News & updates

Machine learning Workshop

Peter Dueben / ECMWF

The Machine learning for weather and climate modelling workshop in Oxford that was partly funded by ESIWACE2 went very well with a lot of interesting talks, posters and discussions. I have written a science blog about it: <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/about/media-centre/science-blog/2019/will-machine-learning-replace-conventional-weather>

ESDM Performance on Non-volatile memory (NVDIMMs)

Luciana R Pedro / University of Reading

ESDM was tested on the NextGenIO Prototype with a first naive approach (using the PMEM interface). This first analysis was run on four dual-socket nodes accessing 80 GByte of data. The theoretical HW performance per node considering 12 NVDIMMs is: write 96 GB/s and read 36 GB/s. The Max Test explores the best-case performance with a single file.

Open call for ESiWACE Services

Service 1 on HPC: Bull Atos in collaboration with NLeSC have set up the call for Service 1 of the HPC user-services proposing “Model portability and refactoring” services. To successful proposals ATOS and NLeSC will provide guidance, engineering, and advice to improve model efficiency and port models to existing and upcoming computing infrastructure.

Service 2 on HPC: CERFACS set up and released the call for ESiWACE Service 2 on “ Coupling, input, output and workflows”. This service offers Dedicated User Support to developers of weather and climate codes to efficiently use the XIOS I/O server or the OASIS3-MCT coupler. In this context, CERFACS provides technical help to design, upgrade or enhance the implementation of XIOS or OASIS3-MCT in your model(s) and/or set up a tailored and computationally efficient coupled system with performant I/Os. Provided by CERFACS and IPSL, this Service is open to any weather/climate research laboratory in Europe. This year, 2 person-month of Dedicated User Support will be offered for both XIOS and OASIS3-MCT.

Both calls were open for proposals submitted before November 1st 2019, 14:00 CET. See <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpc-userservices> for details

ESiWACE promotional video online

ESiWACE Project office

The ESiWACE promotional video is now available online. The video illustrates the importance of global high-resolution climate and weather simulations and how ESiWACE makes these simulations possible. Find details at <https://www.esiwace.eu/results-1/showroom/video-illustrates-the-reasons-for-and-activities-in-esiwace> or the pure video at our new youtube channel <https://youtu.be/wAnb2rajsFs>

Snapshots

Please add one sentence per partner institution indicating what you are currently working on:

DKRZ

The project management of ESiWACE changed from Philipp and Chiara to Dela, Flo, Chenbo, Melanie. -- Thanks Philipp and Chiara for the great work!

ECMWF

More work was done towards the scientific evaluation of ultra-high-resolution simulations.

MPI-M

To introduce further possibilities for data and workflow management, MPI-M is currently preparing the cdo package to interface to the future ESDM API and the recently released public FDB API of ECMWF. Furthermore, possibilities for outsourcing computing to storage systems and/or compute intensive calculations of the cdo operators to gpu systems are currently evaluated. Working on both these goals, preparation and maintenance of the cdo system is included.

CERFACS

CERFACS participated in the European HPC Training Stakeholder Workshop. This workshop aimed at gathering experts and stakeholders both to define what are the training requirements from different domains/target audiences, and to examine how these requirements may be met by existing or new European and national programmes on HPC training.

BSC

BSC (in collaboration with NLeSC and ECMWF) completed a fully-functional version of IFS 43r3 with full XIOS support. BSC is now performing high resolution NEMO runs to evaluate scalability in Mare Nostrum 4, including tests with mixed precision version of the code.

STFC

STFC presented PSyclone at the ESCAPE2 dissemination workshop at ECMWF.

PSyclone-generated NEMO GPU code (for the ORCA1-SI3-GO8 configuration) running on an NVIDIA V100 now runs at approximately the same speed as a Xeon W-2133 (6-core Skylake). Performance improvement is ongoing.

PSyclone is able to transform very simple Fortran examples to optimised CUDA C by translating to the Stencil Intermediate Representation (SIR) which is then run through the Dawn optimising back-end, which is being developed by MeteoSwiss. The purpose of this work is to explore the possibility of interoperability between DSLs. Work continues towards supporting this route for a NEMO tracer-advection benchmark.

Met Office

LFRic and PSyclone were presented, together with their links to other European weather and climate model and DSL developments, at the Computer Science Seminar Series at the University of Exeter in early October. There was a lot of interest from the audience and we talked about future collaborations and exchange of knowledge.

LFRic will be one of the models represented at the Container Hackathon for Modellers in Lugano in December.

University of Reading

We are currently finishing the compatibility report for the NetCDF integration of ESDM. ESDM supports the basic functionalities of NetCDF and selected features including the Python version of NetCDF. C and Python tests made available by the NetCDF developers were used to check the consistency, and the results are given in the report. The nccopy command-line utility was also applied to verify the equality of the files produced by both tools. Benchmarks were evaluated, and they show promising results when ESDM is used as the middleware.

ICHEC

ICHEC will be providing testing facilities for WP4. ICHEC has automated build systems and continuous testing with automated compilation and deployment, Jenkins servers, and VMs as well as containers on the HPC system Kay.

CMCC

The global ORCA36 ocean-sea ice configuration is based on NEMO4.0 coupled to the sea ice model SI3. Particular attention was given to the initial conditions and the bathymetry. Different atmospheric reanalysis have been tested in short runs. A scalability exercise is in progress.

Development of the MUSCL advection schema by means of the GTClang DSL is ongoing. This version will be compared with the equivalent development of the same numerical kernel by means of PSyClone.

CMCC started the containerisation of the NEMO ocean model in preparation of the ESIWACE2 Containerization Hackathon which will be held at CSCS in Lugano, Dec 3-5.

CMCC is working on the initial design of the ESDM extensions for the processing, analytics and visualization support.

Seagate

Seagate is updating the Clovis data backend to the latest ESDM, updating to the latest Mero system, and doing regression tests.

The projects ESIWACE and ESIWACE2 have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 675191 and 823988